

Annual Report 2022–2023

ÉRUDIT CONSORTIUM

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Érudit²⁵

COALITION
PUBLICA

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25 Years of Open Knowledge

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Forewords

A large graphic consisting of a red circle on the left and a dark blue shape on the right, resembling a stylized '25'. The text '25 Years!' is written in white, bold, sans-serif font across the center of these shapes. The background is a white grid with scattered red, yellow, and blue dots and shapes.

25 Years!

Foreword from the Chairman of the Board

This year, we are celebrating Érudit's ongoing 25-year commitment to the dissemination of knowledge and the promotion of bibliodiversity. This anniversary marks a major step in the history of this Québec-based shining jewel, which has now crossed borders into Canada and beyond. Since its creation in 1998, a time when the Internet was still in its infancy, Érudit has never stopped growing and evolving. Established since 2004 as an inter-university consortium made up of the Université de Montréal, the Université Laval and the Université du Québec à Montréal, Érudit is today the main digital platform in Canada for the publication and dissemination of journals publishing in the fields of the social sciences and the humanities.

Linguistic diversity, particularly as it relates to the role of French in the sciences, is a key facet of Érudit's activities and, of course, of this year's celebrations. Language plays a fundamental role in the way we understand the world and it is essential that the uniqueness of French be nurtured and amplified. Our mission has always been to provide every citizen with the fruits of research and to ensure that knowledge accessibility is a reality.

Érudit's success has come from the unrelenting work and dedication of its team. Particularly, I want to highlight the efforts made this year on the renewal application we submitted to the Social Sciences and Humanities Research Council for its *Pan-Canadian Access to Knowledge Initiative* grant, a considerable undertaking whose success depended on the collaboration of all members of the team.

Anniversaries are also precious moments for gratitude. A great many thanks to the three associate universities of the Érudit Consortium, the journals, academic libraries, the Fonds de recherche du Québec, the Canada Foundation for Innovation, the Social Sciences and Humanities Research Council and all our partners. Thank you to the team at Érudit and its Board of Directors for their exemplary work. It is a privilege to work with you on this great mission. And above all, thank you to all our readers for their loyalty and their commitment, they are the ones who give our efforts meaning. Thank you all for coming along on this extraordinary adventure.

With your support and your commitment, we can look to the future with enthusiasm and determination, confident that the next 25 years will be filled with discoveries, achievements, and new horizons to strive for together.

Frédéric Bouchard

Chairman of the Érudit Consortium, Dean of the Faculty of Arts and Science and full professor in the Department of Philosophy at the Université de Montréal.

Foreword from the Executive Director

As Executive Director, looking back on the 2022-2023 year fills me with joy. Above all because we are celebrating our 25-year anniversary, but also because the Érudit Consortium is proud of what it managed to accomplish over the last year. Those accomplishments confirm the key role that our infrastructure plays in the scholarly publishing ecosystem, which we are working relentlessly to keep open, fair, sustainable and truly diverse.

The extension of the Partnership for Open Access with the Canadian Research Knowledge Network is one of the highlights for 2023, as it brings together 54 Canadian academic libraries to offer their support to 223 scholarly journals disseminated through the erudit.org platform. This year, we are also celebrating the 10-year anniversary of the Collecto agreement, which provides access to our collections for Quebec's CEGEP and college communities. On top of that, those collections were enriched by the addition of 20 Canadian journals on erudit.org, which raises the number of journals added since 2019 to 100, a growth of 55% over 4 years!

2023 was also marked by the renewal of the Pan-Canadian Knowledge Access Initiative grant provided by the Social Sciences and Humanities Research Council to Coalition Publica, our partnership with the Public Knowledge Project. By creating a framework for regular consultation with all its stakeholders, Coalition Publica plays a decisive role within the Canadian non-profit scholarly publishing community. Our close collaboration with the Partenariat des bibliothèques Universitaires du Québec helped us expand our capacity to serve Québec's student and research communities.

Érudit celebrates its 25 years of existence and I want to highlight the key role that our team plays in this celebration. Every member of that team has worked to continuously develop an absolutely unique expertise, which they share with the communities we serve, and notably with the journals and the researchers at their core. Since the creation of Érudit, the world of scholarly publishing has undergone profound transformations, brought on by the emergence of digital technology. The team at Érudit is following those disruptions closely

as to adapt both its services and the technological infrastructure that enables them, as well as to support journals in this evolving environment.

Covering areas like knowledge mobilization, technological developments and communication with our partners, Érudit's exceptional skill set is the core of our collective effort to realize our vision for a scholarly publishing ecosystem that is fair for all non-profit stakeholders

Finally, I would like to thank our valued partners: the journal teams, university libraries and granting agencies, the Fonds de recherche du Québec, the Social Sciences and Humanities Research Council and the Canada Foundation for Innovation. Your continued support is essential to our mission and to the progression of the accessibility of research results in Canada and abroad.

Tanja Niemann

Executive Director of the Érudit Consortium

OUR MISSION

Érudit supports open digital publishing and research in the arts, humanities, and social sciences.

OUR VISION

Dedicated to open knowledge.

OUR VALUES

- **Common good**
- **Openness**
- **Collaboration**
- **Innovation**

25 Years of Open Knowledge

Érudit was born of a vision for the future: to make research results openly accessible using digital tools and the Internet, technologies that were just emerging in 1998.

In 25 years, thanks to the commitment of the consortium made up of the Université de Montréal, the Université Laval and the Université du Québec à Montréal, as well as its many other partners, Érudit has become a true institution in the world of Canadian research as well as a central platform for digital dissemination. This success has also been the result of the work of many people who promote the spread of knowledge throughout the world.

In this exceptional annual report, we would like to invite you on a journey to explore these 25 years of history together, discovering (or rediscovering) the role of Érudit in knowledge dissemination.

In a Few Words

From the Three Associated Universities in the Érudit Consortium

“On the occasion of this 25th anniversary, I want to salute the considerable impact of this major initiative when it comes to disseminating the results of research in the humanities and social sciences. These benefits were made possible by exceptional collaborative work, driven by the team at Érudit. The Université de Montréal is especially proud to have actively supported since its inception this strategic initiative aimed at promoting the role of French in science, the unhindered flow of knowledge and dialogue between disciplines - all three are priority issues for our institution. Congratulations to the whole team for this major contribution to the advancement of knowledge!”

Marie-Josée Hébert

Vice-Rector, Research, Discovery, Creation and Innovation, Université de Montréal

*Quote translated

“Québec and Canadian scholarly journals are key vectors for disseminating knowledge about our society. By letting them reach an international readership, Érudit has amplified the impact of our researchers on the international scene. Congratulations to Érudit for 25 years of success! I hope with all my heart that the next decades are even more fruitful. Together, we can continue to push knowledge ever forward.”

Eugénie Brouillet

Vice-Rector, Research, Creation and Innovation, Université Laval

*Quote translated

“The erudit.org platform plays an essential role for the community at the Université du Québec à Montréal, and does so on two levels: it is both an indispensable digital resource for our students and faculty, and an unmatched tool for disseminating the work done by our researchers. The articles to which it provides access are the mirror of the richness and the rigour of the research being done in the social sciences, the humanities, the arts and literature within our university. UQAM is proud to be an associate of the Érudit Consortium and wishes it a glowing future for the next 25 years!”

Christian Agbobli

Vice-Rector, Research, Creation and Innovation, Université Laval

*Quote translated

From Our Granting Agencies

“The commitment shown by the Fonds de recherche du Québec in its support for the role of French in scholarly publications takes concrete shape in our multi-year partnership with Érudit. This collaboration contributed to the dissemination of research in the social sciences, the humanities, the arts and literature as well as the results of this research to the population in Québec. It also gives Québec more reach within the Francophonie.”

Rémi Quirion
Chief Scientist
of Québec

*Quote translated

“With a bold, future-looking mandate, the Canada Foundation for Innovation equips researchers to be global leaders in their field and to respond to emerging challenges. A unique Canadian resource that promotes the mobilization of knowledge, innovation and the training of the next generation, Érudit showcases the powerful contribution of the social sciences, humanities and the arts to society.

Érudit has contributed to the creation and sharing of knowledge by establishing a space that enables dialogue among researchers and promotes international recognition for published works by Canadians. This signal contribution is an invaluable resource for the preservation and promotion of knowledge and ideas.”

Roseann O'Reilly Runte
President and CEO,
Canada Foundation for Innovation

“It is with pride that the Fonds de recherche du Québec – Société et culture provides financial support to close to 60 scholarly journals as well as to Érudit’s digital infrastructure. Open science has come a long way over the years. The sustainability of an initiative of Érudit’s calibre is a source of delight, as it maximizes the discoverability of local researchers and helps them better reach the large international networks.”

Louise Poissant

Scientific Director at the Fonds de recherche du Québec – Société et culture

*Quote translated

“As a federal research funding agency with a mandate to promote and support the humanities and social sciences, the Social Sciences and Humanities Research Council (SSHRC) recognizes the importance of Érudit’s mission to support open digital publishing and research across our disciplines. As a partner of Érudit, we thank this organization for its leadership in democratizing access to knowledge and fostering open knowledge in Canada and around the world.”

Ted Hewitt

President, Social Sciences and Humanities Research Council (SSHRC)

The Digital Revolution

The 1990s, an Uncertain Context for Scholarly Publishing

In the 1990s, the “Periodical Crisis” highlighted the dynamics at play in the post-war world of scholar publishing. The spectacular increase in the price of subscription to scholarly journals, which had begun in the preceding decade, greatly outpaced the growth of the budgets given to libraries. An unfavourable balance of power had been established for academic institutions, forcing them to make agonizing choices in their acquisitions. Research communities did not have a guaranteed access to new knowledge anymore. This crisis came essentially from the pressure generated by a small number of commercial publishers, like Elsevier, Springer and Wiley, who dominate the market for scholarly journals. Notably, these companies, who prioritize profit over knowledge sharing, have enacted disproportionate subscription fees, thereby maintaining considerable profit margins. But they have also created a tendency for uniformization in the scholarly publishing landscape

by acquiring a large number of journals, smoothing out their uniqueness over time. This is notably the case for linguistic diversity, which saw its decline accelerated by the exclusive and hegemonic place given to English.

The 1990s saw the dawn of the World Wide Web and its rapid deployment to numerous spheres of activity. It did not take long for some people to realize that the Internet’s unprecedented structure, based on hypertext links connecting documents in a criss-crossing pattern, had the potential to revolutionize publishing in general and scholarly publishing in particular. The Web, which provides access to a quasi-unlimited number of documents, would allow for a considerable increase in scholarly dissemination. For journals, online publishing would reduce publishing and dissemination costs. This unprecedented visibility was seen as a new way of sharing knowledge, promising to make subscription publishing less lucrative and give journals a degree of independence from commercial publishers.

Érudit's First Steps

Érudit was one of the very first digital publishing initiatives for scholarly journals in Québec, launched in the second half of the 1990s. The project was developed within the Presses de l'Université de Montréal (PUM), where a section called the "Direction des publications électroniques" (Directorate for Electronic Publishing), created in 1996–1997, had the objective of helping scholarly journals transition to the digital world. The PUM put in place a pilot project for two of their journals, *Géographie physique et Quaternaire* and *Surfaces*, and wished to eventually extend it to others.

The very first version of Érudit – an acronym of *É*dition de *revues* *universitaires* et *diffusion* sur les *inforoutes* (Publishing of academic journals and diffusion on the information highway) – saw the light of day in 1998. This structure allowed for both the digital production of articles, so they could be displayed on the Internet, as well as their online dissemination. To these everyday editorial production activities were quickly added the first projects for retrospective collection digitalization, starting with the journals *Meta* and *Sociologie et sociétés*.

"Very early on, we realized that a process aimed at setting up a publicly funded national infrastructure aimed primarily at Québec's humanities and social sciences journal community would have to bring together the skills, commitments and institutional will capable of supporting such a project."

Learn more about the genesis of Érudit through [an interview with its founders](#), Guylaine Beaudry and Gérard Boismenu.

*Quote translated

A Few Key Dates

1996-1997

Creation by the Presses de l'Université de Montréal of the precursor to Érudit, the "Direction des publications électroniques," whose activities focus mainly on a digital transition for scholarly journals.

1999

Digitization of the first retrospective collections with the archiving of two journals, *Meta* and *Sociologie et sociétés*.

1998

Launch of the first version of the Érudit platform, under the supervision of Guylaine Beaudry and Gérard Boismenu.

2001

Unveiling of the second version of the Érudit platform, providing access to close to 6,000 documents.

2004

Creation of the Consortium as a general partnership, with the Université de Montréal, the Université Laval and the Université du Québec à Montréal as its partner members.

2006

Launch of a service for subscription management allowing for the commercialization of scholarly journals disseminated through Érudit, which provided access to around 15,000 articles at that time.

2010

Launch of the third version of the platform with improvements to several services: advanced search functions, trilingual platform, exporting of bibliographical notices. An important retrospective digitalization project is also realized, covering 60,000 articles drawn from the member cultural journals of the SODEP.

2014

Érudit is recognized as a Major Science Initiative (MSI) by the Canada Foundation for Innovation. Érudit is the only MSI for the social sciences, the humanities, the arts and literature.

2013

Consolidation of the Theses section with the signature of an agreement with four Québec universities: UQAM, UQAT, UQTR, UQAC. Through this project, more than 55,000 theses were added to the referencing on the platform that year.

2015

Launch of the Partnership for Open Access developed with the Canadian Research Knowledge Network. This agreement passed with 53 Canadian academic libraries is historical as it transforms a commercial agreement into a collaborative effort to financially support journals disseminated in open access.

2017

Launch of the fourth version of the Érudit platform, with an improved reading experience, an optimization of the dissemination and referencing of documents and preparations for new future services. Over 150,000 articles were available.

2018

Érudit and the Public Knowledge Project collaborated to create Coalition Publica, a partnership with the objective of building a national, open and non-profit infrastructure dedicated to research, dissemination and digital scholarly publishing.

2019

Creation of massive sets of textual data for research purposes in digital humanities, and of bibliometric datasets for studying the scholarly publishing ecosystem itself.

2020

Launch of the Pan-Canadian Access to Knowledge Initiative by the SSHRC, which supports Coalition Publica's activities in order to support discoverability and the impact of Canadian research in the humanities and social sciences, both in Canada and abroad.

2021

The Fonds de recherche du Québec – Société et culture (FRQSC) increased their support for the services provided by Érudit through the AGORA program. This support strengthened the ties which already existed between Érudit and the FRQSC, and allowed for the digital processing of funded and recommended journals.

2023

Érudit turns 25!

37 team members

An interuniversity consortium, which includes Université de Montréal, Université Laval and Université du Québec à Montréal

A corpus with +200,000 publications, mostly covering the social sciences and the humanities

A dissemination platform developed in open source

An infrastructure for digital scholarly publishing

At the Heart of the Research Cycle

Érudit disseminates over 300 journals and 200,000 articles, whose circulation, visibility and discoverability are enhanced by a digital production chain specifically designed for scientific publishing. This work relies on all the best practices established in the contemporary scholarly publishing sector, notably when it comes to the curation of metadata associated with the articles' textual content.

1

Produce

Read by human beings, but also by machines

From the text file sent by the journal teams, we produce a structured digital document in the XML format, combining the full text of the article and its metadata. As a result, this document can be accessed in different reading formats (PDF, HTML, ePub) and indexed by search engines.

2

Disseminate

Accessible everywhere, for many use cases

Structured articles are now accessible from the erudit.org platform through the exploration tools we have created and which provide many different ways to search through the content. The articles are also found through other discovery tools, such as aggregators and search engines with which we have signed agreements (Ebsco, Google Scholar, Crossref, Isidore, etc.).

3

Preserve

Sustainable access for thousands of issues

The long-term preservation of the issues produced and disseminated on our platform is ensured by our partner Portico, who stores our entire corpus on separate protected servers. In doing so, these digital documents will remain accessible in the future, even if reading formats evolve and our own servers disappear.

5

Innovate

For the future of the social sciences and the humanities

As an expert in digital scholarly publishing, Érudit is at the bleeding edge of the evolving technological developments and practices in its field. By leveraging this expertise for numerous research projects, we are promoting innovation in the fields of the social sciences and the humanities.

4

Support

Each journal is unique

Our support for editorial teams comes with bespoke support for their digital publishing and dissemination projects. It also includes the publication and sharing of documentation and guides, and the regular hosting of webinars covering key current issues in the world of scholarly publishing. Our support is also financial, the Partnership for Open Access is an innovative model for creating agreements with libraries, which allows for the redistribution of funds to all journals, including those in immediate open access.

Our Main Impacts

Promote Québec and Canadian Research Around the World

75% of scholarly article views on the erudit.org platform come from outside Canada, with users in more than 200 countries! Among the countries who use our platform the most, we find France, the United States, Germany, Morocco, and Belgium.

Support and Increase Bibliodiversity

The journals disseminated on erudit.org are representative of the richness of the research being done in the social sciences, the humanities, the arts and literature. These journals are editorially independent and are published by a scholarly society, a university press or an academic unit (faculty, department, research group). Most of these publish in French, or bilingually in French and English.

Facilitate Access to Research Results

On top of working in close collaboration with online document repositories and databases such as Google Scholar or the DOAJ, Érudit has established over 1,200 agreements with libraries and documentary institutions worldwide, ensuring wide distribution of its corpus.

Develop A Viable Economic Model

Journals can choose to be disseminated on Érudit in immediate open access or behind a 12-month moving wall, in accordance with relevant public policy. Revenue from subscription fees is redistributed to the journals in restricted access, while the Partnership for Open Access provides financial support for journals in immediate open access. This hybrid model ensures both economic support for the journals and access to a majority of the research.

Contribute to a Knowledge-Based Society

In a context where disinformation is becoming more prevalent and where the distinction between different sources on the Internet is not readily apparent, guaranteeing open and easy access to thorough and serious scientific and cultural resources for college students has become essential. With its policy of open access and its strategy for content discoverability, Érudit is proud to contribute to the democratization of knowledge.

Commitments to Open Science

Érudit's commitment to open science takes many forms and covers complementary activities, both nationally and abroad:

+ Paving the Road to Diamond Open Access!

Like all Canadian scholarly journals, the majority of journals on Érudit now publish in immediate open access, which is becoming the norm worldwide, although business models vary. Canadian journals in the social sciences and the humanities are characterized by their independence, their non-profit ethos and the fact that they give centre stage to Canadian issues, but also by their adoption of a fair publishing model, namely diamond open access.

Indeed, readers can access these journals for free, and authors do not have to pay any publication fees (APC) to get published. Diamond open access is financially viable because of the contributions made by universities, libraries and granting agencies. Direct funding of journals in the social sciences and the humanities by national granting agencies - the Social Sciences and Humanities Research Council (SSHRC) and the Fonds de recherche du Québec - Société et culture (FRQSC) - contributes to creating a unique funding system in the Western world. This is a fair and sustainable publishing model, which lets the whole of society benefit from the scientific knowledge being developed, which facilitates further knowledge advances.

Journals publishing in diamond open access are the ideal publication venues for researchers in the social sciences and the humanities, as they generally have little research funding to pay the publication fees charged by commercial publishers. These journals promote publication in both Canadian official languages and drive greater bibliodiversity in scholarly publishing, for metrics like research topic diversity, publishing stakeholders, publication formats and language.

Diamond open access is recommended by several international organizations and initiatives, such as UNESCO, the Budapest Open Access Initiative and Science Europe. The Coalition Publica team gave its support to the Action Plan for Diamond Open Access, while producing a response to that document.

“In Latin America, as in Canada, universities act as the main publishers of social sciences and humanities journals and play an essential role in the development of institutional and regional platforms for dissemination and open access to journals (e.g., Latindex, Redalyc, SciELO, CLACSO). In an international context of open science, where collaborative production of knowledge with nonacademic social actors, bibliodiversity, multilingualism, collaborative and non-commercial publishing models, as well as the reappraisal of academic evaluation criteria are being promoted, the work done by initiatives such as Érudit is essential, and we extend our warmest congratulations on its 25th anniversary.”

Karina Batthyány

Executive Director of the Consejo Latinoamericano de Ciencias Sociales (CLACSO)

*Quote translated

+ Promoting Science in French

Érudit was asked at the end of 2022 to speak before the Standing Committee on Science and Research of the House of Commons of Canada as part of its study on **Research and Scientific Publication in French**. We presented our commitments to bibliodiversity and the dissemination of French-language publications, and reminded the Committee of the essential role that journals play in the research cycle. To support that committee’s work, we also submitted a document titled **Brief on research and scientific publication in French**. After several consultations, the Committee submitted its official report to the House of Commons.

[Read the official report](#)

That report notably highlights that “the dominance of English threatens the dissemination of scientific knowledge in French” and that this dominance “could mean that local research topics are overlooked, particularly those relating to Canadian Francophone communities themselves.” To address this situation, the report provides a series of recommendations to support research in French.

“The ACFAS would like to wish its long-time ally Érudit a very happy anniversary! For 25 years now, Érudit has been an invaluable space to showcase French-language scientific knowledge. Through its visionary and innovative approach, the Érudit platform has, over the years, forged itself a leading position in the digital scholarly publishing community both in Canada and internationally. The hard work done by the Érudit team in democratizing access to knowledge and making French-language scholarly content discoverable is essential to ensuring the vitality of our scientific and intellectual heritage. Thank you, and long live Érudit!”

Sophie Montreuil

Managing director for the Association Francophone pour le savoir (Acfas)

*Quote translated

+ Contribute to Standards and Best Practices

In terms of both the technical and the editorial side, the adoption of established standards and practices promotes the spread of open science and recognition of its quality.

The standards adopted by Érudit for its platform enable greater interoperability with other systems: our journals can be integrated into other research tools, making their articles easier to find. Among these standards and best practices, we can highlight DOI, OAI-PMH, KBART 2014 and Z39.50, which all contribute to an increased discoverability for articles. Moreover, adopting other standards allows us to integrate external content into our platform, adding to the articles we disseminate directly. As an example, Érudit has been collaborating with **ORCID-CA** since 2021 on a project to integrate ORCID identifiers to the platform. ORCID is a unique identifier used to distinguish authors who share the same name.

Érudit’s team members also participate in various national and international committees working on evolving best practices in the field. These include the **DIAMAS** project, the **Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ)**, the **National Information Standards Organization (NISO)**, **CO-OPERAS**, and **Crossref**.

And finally, Érudit supports journals as they work to implement best publishing practices, both in a personalized manner with each editorial team or through the creation of various documents, such as the [Preparing Quality Metadata in OJS](#) guide and the [Open Science](#) research note. Among our support initiatives, we can also mention the project to include our journals into the DOAJ. This ensures that the journals conform to national and international scientific policies, notably for open access.

“In 2003, Érudit appeared as a natural partner for the project that would become Persée. It went beyond sharing tools, as we worked to make our sites interoperable, to increase the visibility of scientific content published in French. Together, Persée and Érudit decided to expand the scope of the OAI-PMH protocol so that metadata could be shared, but also the full text of every one of their documents. The protocol was proposed to other Francophone stakeholders (revues.org and the brand-new CAIRN). The ‘Francophone network’ thus created became a particularly rich space to share practices and data. Over the years, the need for interoperability between platforms became self-evident and the notion of open science became part of the landscape, but we should highlight the pioneer role that this network played, and particularly Érudit’s role within it.”

Viviane Boulétreau

Lead, IT and Development,
Persée

*Quote translated

+ Provide Unique Access to French-Language Textual Data

For several years now, Érudit has been providing access to the [Coalition Publica data repository](#), a vast collection of documents that includes both articles published on the erudit.org platform and digitized collections from our partners such as Library and Archives Canada, Bibliothèque et Archives nationales du Québec and Canadiana/CRKN. This substantial corpus is designed to stimulate research that relies on methods adapted to big data, in various fields such as linguistics, history and economics. Over the last year, an important update was made to this collection, which doubled its volume from 12 to 24 terabytes. The collection is now one of the largest corpora of textual data in French available for research in the world.

+ Better Understanding Journals

To function, scholarly journals require certain resources, notably financial means. However, a closer analysis shows that budgetary criteria are not the sole predictors of whether a journal runs well, which depends greatly on the context in which it operates. In other words, scientific publishing is not split between “poor and flawed” journals on one side, and “rich and healthy” ones on the other. The situation is more nuanced.

To promote a better understanding of this issue, the team working on research for the Érudit Consortium prepared a research note (in both French and English), detailing the factors that support healthy journals.

[Read the research note](#)

Evolution of the Corpus and Its Dissemination

Evolution of the Corpus

NUMBER OF JOURNALS

■ SCHOLARLY JOURNALS ■ CULTURAL JOURNALS

322

JOURNALS ARE DISSEMINATED THROUGH THE ERUDIT.ORG PLATFORM IN 2023

INCLUDING

- 142 JOURNALS IN OPEN ACCESS
- 112 JOURNALS BEHIND A MOVING WALL
- 68 ARCHIVED JOURNALS

SINCE 2018, AROUND 20 NEW JOURNALS HAVE BEEN ADDED EACH YEAR TO THE ERUDIT.ORG PLATFORM, MOST OF THEM IN OPEN ACCESS.

EVOLUTION OF THE NUMBER OF ARTICLES DISSEMINATED

239,135

AVAILABLE ARTICLES

WITH

10,329

NEWLY DISSEMINATED
THIS YEAR

*Year 2023 incomplete

Focus on Scholarly Journals

MODE OF PUBLICATION OF THE SCIENTIFIC ARTICLES
NEWLY DISSEMINATED THIS YEAR

■ MOVING WALL ■ OPEN ACCESS

WE REACHED AN IMPORTANT MILESTONE IN 2022: MORE THAN HALF OF THE SCHOLARLY ARTICLES ADDED THAT YEAR TO THE COLLECTION WERE IMMEDIATELY AVAILABLE IN OPEN ACCESS!

 98%

OF SCHOLARLY ARTICLES DISSEMINATED ON ERUDIT.ORG ARE AVAILABLE IN OPEN ACCESS

ACTIVE SCIENTIFIC JOURNALS SORTED BY THEIR PUBLISHING LANGUAGE

EN FR FR/EN BILINGUAL OR PLURILINGUAL*

*Including: French, English, Italian, Portuguese, Spanish, German.

GENDER OF FIRST AUTHORS

■ MEN ■ WOMEN

Genders are identified based on the authors' first names. This method overlooks the presence of non-gendered authors. We acknowledge that several individuals publishing on the platform are non-binary, and we emphasize the limitations of the method used.

Dissemination

NUMBER OF PAGES VIEWED ON THE ERUDIT.ORG PLATFORM

+67% ↑

+67% INCREASE IN THE NUMBER OF PAGE VIEWS IN THE LAST FIVE YEARS!

NUMBER OF UNIQUE USERS PER YEAR ON THE ERUDIT.ORG PLATFORM

+70% ↑

+70% INCREASE IN THE NUMBER OF UNIQUE USERS IN THE LAST FIVE YEARS!

USER DEVICES
TO ACCESS ÉRUDIT:

70%
FROM A
COMPUTER

29%
FROM A
SMARTPHONE

1%
FROM A
TABLET

TOP 10 COUNTRIES FOR VIEWS
IN 2022 (CALENDAR YEAR):

24.6% CANADA

20.3% FRANCE

11.7% UNITED STATES

25.1% OTHER COUNTRIES

4.4% GERMANY

3.3% MOROCCO

2.5% CAMEROON

2.2% IVORY COAST

2.1% ALGERIA

2.1% BELGIUM

1.7% DEMOCRATIC
REPUBLIC OF
THE CONGO

WORLD DISTRIBUTION OF ARTICLE VIEWS

CONSULTATIONS, TOTAL

10	1 000	100 000	1 000 000	6 000 000
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CONSULTATIONS PER MILLION INHABITANTS

10 1 000 1 000 000

A horizontal color gradient bar ranging from dark blue on the left to red on the right, with a yellow-green section in the middle. It is used to represent the density of consultations per million inhabitants.

1.7 M\$ CAD

GIVEN TO JOURNALS DURING
FISCAL YEAR 2022-2023

This income, which supports the editorial work done by journals, comes from agreements made with libraries as part of the Partnership for Open Access or from the commercialization of subscriptions sold to institutions.

Among the articles which have generated the most interest this year in the 1,200 libraries with subscriptions to Érudit or partnered with it, we find the following titles:

→ L'anxiété de performance à l'enfance et l'adolescence : état des connaissances cliniques et scientifiques

Soucisse, M. M. & Heins, M.-P. (2021).
Revue québécoise de psychologie, 42(3), 43-73.
<https://doi.org/10.7202/1084579ar>

→ Problème social : le concept et les principales écoles théoriques

Mayer, R. & Laforest, M. (1990).
Service social, 39(2), 13-43.
<https://doi.org/10.7202/706475ar>

→ Bienfaits psychologiques de l'activité physique pour la santé mentale optimale

Poiré, E. (2017).
Santé mentale au Québec, 42(1), 147-164.
<https://doi.org/10.7202/1040248ar>

→ Pensionnats autochtones : impact intergénérationnel

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25 Years of Helping Journals

Érudit was created to support journals in the digital world. Twenty-five years later, that is still our mission. We are delighted to have received several testimonials from editorial teams on the occasion of our 25th anniversary. We would like to share a few with you:

“The creation of Érudit two and a half decades ago was visionary. UVic Libraries’ own internationally recognized, peer-reviewed, open-access journal, KULA: Knowledge Creation, Dissemination, and Preservation Studies, is part of Coalition Publica and benefits from the robust dissemination infrastructure provided by Érudit. Their indexing services are essential for ensuring discoverability of the content that we publish, ensuring that the work we and our contributors put such care into producing reaches as wide an audience as possible. We look forward to working with Érudit over the next quarter of a century, for the benefit of Canadian-based research and research infrastructure.”

Samantha MacFarlane

Co-editor-in-chief, *KULA: Knowledge Creation, Dissemination, and Preservation Studies*

“Érudit contributes to the development of our journal by ensuring its dissemination around the world in a high-quality format.”

Georges L. Bastin

Managing Editor, *Meta*

*Quote translated

*“Érudit’s dedication to open access publishing is commendable in an era of steep library pricing and pay-per-essay publishing that limits rather than expands our access to knowledge. Érudit means increased access and longevity for *Monstrum*, now in its sixth year of publication. As we expand to biannual publication and begin to receive more submissions from across the globe, Érudit’s support is essential in our goal to reach a diverse readership.”*

Kristopher Woofter

Editor-in-Chief, *Monstrum*

“The Canadian Medical Education Journal’s partnership with Érudit has been an excellent opportunity to enhance its French publication endeavors. As a Canadian academic journal, it is important that it is able to provide content in both English and French. As a reputable digital platform, Érudit has amplified the visibility of CMEJ’s French-language research and facilitated access to a diverse range of scholarly content for French-speaking medical and health professionals. We have thoroughly enjoyed working with Érudit over the past two years, and look forward to continued collaboration.”

Marcel D’Eon and Heather Hickey
Canadian Medical Education Journal

“Ontario History, a journal published by the Ontario Historical Society, wants to sincerely congratulate Érudit. Since the beginning of our relationship in 2015, we have had the pleasure and the privilege of working with its talented and diligent staff. The international readership of our journal on the platform has grown exponentially. We want to salute the important work that Érudit does and to thank it for its support, which has allowed us to transition sustainably to an open access model. Cheers to Érudit!”

Sarah McCabe
Project Manager and Librarian,
The Ontario Historical Society
*Quote translated

“Erudit offers very generous financial support for open access journals like the Trumpeter, without which our journal would not have been able to make improvements to the hosting arrangements for its servers.”

Nathan Kowalsky
editor, *The Trumpeter*

“Érudit is a Canada-based platform for distributing mainly non-scientific journals, and we are happy to be one of the few science journals in the group. Thank you for providing us with access to subscribers and potential readers far beyond what we would reach in the traditional geoscience publishing world.”

Sandra Barr

editor of *Atlantic Geoscience*

“Érudit has provided the Diamond OA journal that I edit with visibility, a professional profile, archiving, and better dissemination. It has also raised issues with me that I hadn’t thought of, concerning the above topics.”

Dominik Wujastyk

Editor and founder,
History of Science in South Asia

“I hope that Érudit will grow and accompany more and more journals, while preserving the qualities that are its hallmark: irreplaceable and human.”

Jean Marie Bioteau

Associate Editor,
Santé mentale au Québec

*Quote translated

“Érudit has become an invaluable partner for the dissemination of scholarship published by Canadian SSH journals. By drawing on the expertise of those working at Érudit, our journals have realized growth in their readership as well as general benefits to their respective publishing programs. This level of expertise and growth is difficult for many smaller, independent, Canadian journals to develop on their own. Érudit has proven to be an essential publishing partner for many Canadian journals.”

Kathy Killoh

Interim Director,
Athabasca University Press

Structuring Activities

Guided by our principles of open access and science, the activities at Érudit are also aligned with our **strategic plan** and the one laid out for the **Coalition Publica**, the partnership between Érudit and the Public Knowledge Project.

Coalition Publica

+ **Commitments and Community Consultations**

Understanding the needs of the communities we support is the priority of the Coalition Publica team. To help us in this task, and to promote closer collaboration between the team members at Érudit and PKP, we did the following this year:

- Solidified internal governance by reviewing the mandates and organizational structure of the existing work groups.
- Reinforced participation of our core user groups to the governance structure of Coalition Publica. The user journal group and the user library group, both newly formed, have begun their work this year.
- Created a new work group focused on the community and engagement.

Interviews with librarians and journal editorial teams were conducted by Jeanette Hatherill (consultant in strategic community development) in order to better understand their priorities, and provide us with feedback on what tools, resources and advice we could develop to support open access publications.

Finally, to further pool our collective efforts, several members from the Érudit, PKP and Coalition Publica teams have been invited to join the Canadian Community Development Working Group, put together by the **Library Publishing Coalition**. One of that group's mandate is to mobilize stakeholders from the ecosystem of Canadian scientific publishing to promote the development of a strong community of consulting libraries in Canada.

“PKP is honoured to collaborate with Érudit through our joint initiative, Coalition Publica, to increase the accessibility and visibility of scholarly and community-based content from across the country. With the support of the Canadian Foundation for Innovation and the Social Sciences and Humanities Research Council, Coalition Publica is building a strong, open and inclusive research infrastructure that will enhance our collective impact.

We are excited to continue and strengthen our partnership with Érudit to pursue our common vision of a diamond open access future, where diverse and locally relevant knowledge is shared globally for the benefit of the public.”

Kevin Stranack

Operations Director,
Public Knowledge Project

+ Funding Through the Pan-Canadian Knowledge Access Initiative Program

The teams at Érudit and PKP were widely involved at the beginning of 2023 in the submission to the SSHRC of a renewal request for the **Pan-Canadian Access to Knowledge Initiative** grant. We are pleased that this funding has been confirmed and announced this fall, and grateful to the SSHRC for its support, which will help sustain our operations for the next six years (2023–2029).

Thanks to this renewed support, Coalition Publica will continue to expand the services it provides to journals, particularly in terms of interoperability and conformity with international standards, and to contribute to research on scholarly publishing itself. This funding will allow Coalition Publica to increase discoverability and visibility for the social sciences research being done in Canada and abroad.

+ Guide to Improve Metadata

One of the goals for the **Coalition Publica** initiative is to support Canadian scholarly journals disseminated on the erudit.org platform that use Open Journal Systems (OJS). For most of these journals, we have implemented a gateway between Érudit and OJS that harvests the metadata from files produced through OJS and that then uploads them to erudit.org. With the objective of improving this process even further, a guide on the most important metadata for the dissemination of journal issues on Érudit was created. This guide, available in both French and English, is free for both consultation and sharing. It will be regularly updated to reflect the evolution of OJS and respond to comments from user journals.

Consult the Guide

+ Presentations

The community's interest for Coalition Publica remains strong and our team was invited to present the partnership and its initiatives at more than a dozen conferences and events.

“The University of Alberta Library has been an enthusiastic supporter of Érudit for many years. As a rare example of a non-commercial, scholar-led publishing platform, Érudit, and its innovative Coalition Publica partnership with the Public Knowledge Project, is building a more equitable, sustainable, and open future for Canadian scholarly journal publishing.”

Dale Askey and Sonya Betz

Library of the University
of Alberta

Digital Publishing

+ New Journals in 2023

An entire year of important work goes into the integration of each new journal to our dissemination platform. First, candidate journals are evaluated by Érudit's scientific leadership team based on criteria aligned with those used by granting agencies in Québec and Canada. Once the journals are accepted, and depending on their profile, the candidate journals go through several steps, such as undergoing an evaluation of production costs, and choosing processing and dissemination options (open access or access barrier). During the whole process, employees specialized in digital publishing answer questions from journals, helping to inform and support them in their decision-making.

In 2023, 20 journals were added to erudit.org. Most newly added journals are available in open access. Their activities are supported by the academic libraries of their host institutions, who host instances of Open Journal System and provide them with technical support and practical advice.

Access the catalogue
of new titles

+ Archiving Projects

We upload several thousand pages of archive material every year, a major undertaking carried out in close collaboration with the journal teams. Digitized and structured following best practices, these archives provide access to older articles with content that remains extremely relevant for research. Among the important digitalization projects this year, we find the following journals:

- 📄 *Mesure et évaluation en éducation, 1995 to 2007*
- 📄 *Sociocultural community development and practices, with every issue since 2010*
- 📄 *Human Development, Disability, and Social Change, 2009 to 2019*
- 📄 *Recherches qualitatives, 1999 to 2017*
- 📄 *Petite revue de philosophie, 1979 to 1990*

“As editor of Encounters in Theory and History of Education, I would like to congratulate Érudit on its 25th Anniversary and express our gratitude for its excellent work. The personnel has always been ready to respond to questions and to help us do a better work. We appreciate the dissemination of our work in French.”

Rosa Bruno Jofré

Co-founding Senior Editor,

Calvin Bowry

Managing Editor,

Encounters in Theory and History of Education

+ Automatic Generation of PDF Files

In recent years, several scholarly journals have stopped publishing a print version of their issues. To help them provide a PDF version of their articles on the platform, we have deployed a tool that allows for the automatic generation and dissemination of a PDF version drawn from the XML structure of their content.

Access and Dissemination

+ Transition to Open Access

Every year, several journals move their dissemination model toward immediate open access, and in 2023, seven scholarly journals made that transition. Moving to open access requires several analytical and validation steps: analysis of the journal's profile, impact on journal funding, signature of commitments, review of author contracts and licenses. In some situations, journals need several years of transition before moving to open access.

The transition to open access is the fruit of careful reflection, and requires considerable work on the part of a journal's team. Once the decision is taken, substantial efforts need to be deployed to review a journal's editorial policies as well as its internal operations. In the end, those efforts are rewarded as articles available in open access have much more visibility.

Here are the seven journals who have transitioned to open access in 2023:

- 📄 *Aequitas*
- 📄 *Les Cahiers de la Société québécoise de recherche en musique*
- 📄 *Cinémas*
- 📄 *Material Culture Review / Revue de la culture matérielle*
- 📄 *Relations industrielles / Industrial Relations*
- 📄 *Revue de Droit de l'Université de Sherbrooke*
- 📄 *Sociologie et sociétés*

“The Sociologie et sociétés journal decided to move to open access on January 1, 2023. Érudit’s support has been particularly valuable. Its team helped us as we thought through every important element of the transition, while also helping us to draw up a portrait of the financial impact of moving to open access. A huge thanks to the entire Érudit team for its support!”

Stéphane Moulin
Managing Editor,
Sociologie et sociétés

*Quote translated.

+ Partnership for Open Access

We are pleased to announce that the Partnership for Open Access (POA), established with the Canadian Research Knowledge Network (CRKN), was extended for an additional two years. This extension will act as a period of transition toward a new long-term partnership agreement for 2025 and will allow our organizations to develop an ambitious model for open access that is adapted to the Canadian context.

The POA is based on a collaborative model that provides stable financial support to 223 Canadian scholarly journals disseminated through the erudit.org platform. As part of a global transformation of scholarly publishing, the POA brings together Canadian libraries and journals to create a fair and sustainable open access publishing environment. The **two-year extension of the CRKN-Érudit Partnership for Open Access** took effect on January 1, 2023, and impacts 54 participating CRKN member institutions.

“The Partnership for Open Access between the Canadian Research Knowledge Network (CRKN) and Érudit is integral to CRKN’s goal to advance interconnected, sustainable access to knowledge. Through this partnership, our members champion bibliodiversity and sustainability in the Canadian scholarly landscape and enable access to vital content in both of Canada’s official languages.”

Érudit is CRKN’s trusted partner and our relationship has only grown stronger as we approach our tenth year of partnership. We look forward to a future of strong partnership and collaboration that will continue to expand and enrich the open digital knowledge ecosystem in Canada.”

Clare Appavoo

Executive Director,
Canadian Research Knowledge Network

+ Presentation of the New Support Model for Open Access

The entire scholarly publishing sector is currently going through an important transition. Érudit and the publications it disseminates are part of that: several journals have moved to complete open access and several of our subscription agreements have evolved toward the model provided by the Partnership for Open Access. The need to take into account these changes and their impacts on the financial stability of journals led us to work, with the help of our Scientific Committee, on reviewing the ways in which the funds coming from libraries as part of the Partnership for Open Access were redistributed to the journals, with the objective of a greater degree of equity among them.

+ Ten Years of Collaboration Between Érudit and Collecto!

We were happy to celebrate the ten-year anniversary of the agreement between Érudit and Collecto and its renewal by the 54 member-libraries for the next five years! Since 2002, this agreement has allowed 144,000 CEGEP students and teachers to access the largest corpus of humanities and social science journals in Canada.

[Read the statement](#)

It promotes greater equity among CEGEPs when it comes to access to Québec and Canadian journals, as well as providing sustainable financial support for the editorial teams working on those journals. Contributions from college libraries are essential to scholarly and cultural journals disseminated on Érudit, as they are often small and financially fragile.

“Érudit was created around the same time I started my university studies, and it still follows me today in my job. From literature student to teacher of French literature at the CEGEP de Lanaudière in L’Assomption, I regularly use Érudit to enrich my research and my teaching. It is a useful tool to find your way in the wide world of scientific and cultural publications, from A to Z! Or rather, from 24 images to XYZ! Happy 25th anniversary to Érudit!”

Catherine Bourassa-Gaudreault

Teacher, CEGEP de Lanaudière

*Quote translated

+ Promote Remote Access

No matter where you are, Érudit supports you in your research. It is in that spirit that we launched during the lockdown of spring 2020 a campaign that we are calling “Érudit at home/Érudit chez vous.” This campaign, aimed at promoting the journals disseminated on erudit.org and the various ways our platform can be accessed, was a complete success. We kept it going with publications on our digital channels, as well as with a series of posters sent to libraries with a subscription or a partnership with Érudit.

[See the campaign](#)

+ Collaboration with Mir@bel: Promote the Visibility of French-language journals

The Mir@bel network has been a long-term partner of Érudit in France. It is a repository of French-language scholarly journals disseminated online, which contains a lot of information about the journals it contains. At the end of 2021, Mir@bel launched the Mir@bel2022 project aimed at positioning French scholarly journals on the world stage with shared, open and quality data about their publishers as well as their access and dissemination policies. The indexing of French journals into the Directory of Open Access Journal (DOAJ) repository being a key objective of the Mir@bel2022 project, we met a few times with the members of the Mir@bel network, including Sophie Fotiadi, a coordinator for the network, to share our experience with indexing in this repository. We also shared documentation related to our own DOAJ indexing project and participated in various seminars organized by Mir@bel.

[Browse Érudit Journals](#)

“Through their geographic proximity to the team at Persée, the founders of the Mir@bel network have been closely tracking the wonderful evolution of Érudit over the last 20 years. For our network, which brings together a wide range of information professionals (librarians, publishers, etc.), sharing skills and information is a core concern. For this reason, from the start, relationships were established with the main French-language journal portals, including Érudit.

Regular meetings, data sharing, the common project for the referencing of journals in open access: these common achievements allowed us to create important relationships in an ever more open context. These exchanges with Érudit were the entry point into Québec for the Mir@bel base and made it easier to provide our audiences with access to Canadian scholarly journals. Something to watch for another 25 years!”

Sophie Fotiadi

Coordinator, Mir@bel network

*Quote translated

+ Promoting Cultural Journals

The SODEP and Érudit continued their collaboration to provide holiday readings through a **Summer edition** and a **Winter edition** of the Culture to Go project. Come enjoy our selection of articles covering the theme of Québécois heritage and the Holiday season.

We also participated in the Printemps des revues 2023 by presenting a selection of some of the cultural articles on erudit.org that were most viewed in college and academic libraries with a subscription to Érudit.

[See the selection](#)

“Érudit makes a valuable contribution to the literature of ideas and democratic life. I used it a lot, first as a student, then as an editor and writer, to gain access to less intrusive media, to the complex writings of my contemporaries. Through this platform, the journal has really lived again, in a different way. It is not an existence of something floating in formaldehyde or hiding in an archive box; the texts in Liberté have been circulating for a long time, in networks that its small team could not have reached on its own. The journal is read, taught, commented on; it creates a response.

In addition to offering us this wonderful space, the Érudit team supports us with rigour and kindness, while being always available to answer our questions and respond to our (sometimes bizarre) ideas, and providing us with advice on highly specialized subjects.

Thanks for everything!”

Valérie Lefebvre-Faucher

Chief Editor, *Liberté*

*Quote translated

Research and Mobilization of Knowledge

+ Coalition Publica Scholarships

As part of the SSHRC's [Pan-Canadian Access to Knowledge Initiative](#), [Coalition Publica](#) supports the next generation of researchers through a grant program. This program is aimed at supporting research projects that focus on the scholarly communication system and the dissemination of research, or that make use of the textual data corpus developed by Coalition Publica.

The second cohort of Coalition Publica Scholarship recipients has been selected by the committee of researchers associated with the grant. Fifteen project proposals were received, and eight grants were awarded. Projects included the study of collaborative networks and progress toward open science, the measurement of interdisciplinary research, and the interaction between open metadata systems and decentralized systems.

Examples of two projects with grants awarded by Coalition Publica:

1. Assessing open access scholarly communication practices of early and mid-career researchers in Canada

“My research focused on open access scholarly communications practices among researchers in Canada. Open access to research results is essential to promote and ensure fair access to scientific information and knowledge. Since researchers are interested in creating and communicating knowledge, I focused on researchers working in the social sciences and the humanities (SSH) from the U15. Indeed, studies have shown that the adoption of open access in the SSH has been lower than in STEM fields. I wanted to understand the factors responsible for this low adoption rate, as well as the factors likely to positively influence open access publishing practices in researchers. Canada is one of the rare countries with a set of national policies for open access, and it is important to evaluate how much researchers engage in OA publishing. This can help decision makers and open access publishing stakeholders in Canada, and highlight what can be done to increase adoption.”

Philips Ayeni

Doctoral candidate,
School of Information Studies

*Quote translated

Publications and communications for this project:

- Ayeni, P., & Willson, R. (2022). Factors influencing Canadian HASS researchers' open access publishing practices: Implication for the future of scholarly communication. Proceedings of the Annual Conference of CAIS/ Actes Du congrès Annuel De l'ACSI. <https://doi.org/10.29173/cais1245>
- Ayeni, P.O & Willson, R (2022). Investigating open access publishing practices of early and mid-career researchers in Humanities and Social Sciences disciplines. Proceedings of the Association for Information Science and Technology, 59 (398-403) <https://doi.org/10.1002/pa2.641>
- Ayeni, P. (2022, October 26). Poster: Assessing open access scholarly communication practices of early and mid-career researchers in Canada [Poster Presentation]. ALISE 2022 “Go back and Get It: From One Narrative to Many” Pittsburgh, PA <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7259513>

2. The economics of open access publishing: research funding, article processing charges and the revenues of commercial scholarly publishers

“There are numerous challenges when it comes to scholarly communication, but on the issue of open access, the costs of publication under the author-payer (APC) model create inequalities and obstacles, notably for those who work in fields or countries with fewer resources or those who belong to underrepresented groups. That is the problem that I am exploring in my research. My master’s thesis aims to estimate the amounts paid in article processing fees by journals published in open or hybrid access through the five big publishers (Elsevier, Springer-Nature, SAGE, Taylor & Francis, Wiley), and who benefited from funding from the three Canadian granting agencies between 2015 and 2018. I found that authors who mentioned funding from the three agencies over that period collectively paid 25.3 million dollars in APCs, and only 48% of publications who reported funding from the three agencies were published in open access, which means that more than half the authors did not conform to the open access policy established by the three granting agencies for publications.”

Leigh-Ann Butler

Master’s student,
School of Information Studies,
University of Ottawa.

Publications and communications for this project:

- 📄 Funding the Business of Open Access: A Bibliometric Analysis of Article Processing Charges, Research Funding, and the Revenues of the Oligopoly of Publishers
<http://hdl.handle.net/10393/44690>
- 📄 Haustein, Stefanie, & Butler, Leigh-Ann. (2022, May 17). Inequities of Article Processing Charges: How the Oligopoly of Academic Publishers Profits from Open Access. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6557271>
- 📄 Butler, L.-A., Matthias, L., Simard, M.-A., Mongeon, P., & Haustein, S. (2022). The oligopoly’s shift to open access publishing: How for-profit publishers benefit from gold and hybrid article processing charges. *Proceedings of the Annual Conference of CAIS/ Actes Du congrès Annuel De l’ACSI*.
<https://doi.org/10.29173/cais1262>

+ Access to Enhanced Metadata

The team focusing on research created a way to access the metadata from scientific articles published between 2015 and 2021 on the erudit.org platform, making it possible to do research on the Canadian and international scholarly publishing done on the platform. Among the fields populated for each document, we find type of access; language; authors by name, number and rank; institutions of affiliation; country of affiliation and province of affiliation, for Canadian content. This metadata facilitates research on the current state and the tendencies of scholarly publishing in Québec, Canada and worldwide.

This data is available without restriction (license CC0) on Dataverse

+ The “Imaginer l’avenir des revues en sciences humaines et sociales” Symposium

As part of the Acfas Conference for 2022, a symposium titled “*Entre anglicisation de la recherche et libre accès : imaginer l’avenir des revues en sciences humaines et sociales*” (Between increasingly anglicized research and open access: imagining the future of journals in the humanities) aimed to present the issues and challenges that French-language scientific journals face, as do any journal which is not published in English. It brought together dozens of researchers and professionals from the field of scientific dissemination. Here is a summary of the presentations made during this event.

Read the summary

+ 5 Questions With...

What are journals concerned about? What are their big challenges right now? How do scholarly journals contribute to the great debates of the day? To answer these questions and get a better understanding of the reality of Québec and Canadian scholarly journals, we launched the “5 Questions With” interview series.

[Read the first interviews](#)

+ Publication of a Scholarly Article Quantifying Open Access in Canada

In the summer of 2022, the article “[Measuring the prevalence of open access in Canada: A national comparison](#)”, written by Virginie Paquet, Simon van Bellen and Vincent Larivière, was published in *The Canadian Journal of Information and Library Science*. It presents new data on the evolution of open access in Canada, its particularities when it comes to grants and geographic realities, at the provincial and institutional levels. The article’s data was compiled through Dimensions.ai and Érudit’s internal data.

+ Concepts and Knowledge

The objective of the “Concepts and Knowledge” project is to enhance the scientific corpus available on the erudit.org platform, in a pedagogical spirit that would enable knowledge to be disseminated to the general public. In this age of alternative facts and the proliferation of hard-to-verify sources, it becomes more relevant to seek to understand our society by reading or re-reading the analyses patiently constructed by researchers. They are the fruits of several years of intellectual work, submitted and validated by the scientific community before being published in scholarly journals. Through open access, that work is now available to everyone. The project, with identity as its theme, was coordinated by Michelle Edwige Jeanne Martineau, doctoral candidate in political science at the Université de Montréal.

Concepts and Knowledge

+ Social Innovation

To highlight solutions for social innovation, the Réseau québécois en innovation sociale launched a project to gather examples from its members. It is in this context that **Inven T**, a service aimed at supporting social and technosocial innovation at the Université de Montréal, contacted Érudit. Érudit and the Partnership for Open Access are examples of responses to a collective need, in this case access to knowledge, co-developed by a group of stakeholders. This collaboration will contribute to Érudit’s reach into a network of organizations supporting innovations and, more broadly, to the promotion of a collective, non-commercial, open and equitable solution. It will also highlight the diversity of innovations and their potential impacts.

+ UNESCO Chair

We want to congratulate our Scientific Director, Vincent Larivière, who accepted the UNESCO Chair in Open Science. The objective of the Chair is to study practices around open science, their different forms (open access, open data, open peer review), the effects of these practices on the quality of research and on society, as well as the barriers and incentives that can influence their adoption.

Technological Developments

This year saw the closure of several of our large-scale technological projects, like our server migration, and the implementation of new structural projects, like the integration of ORCID identifiers.

+ Migration of Our Servers to the Béluga Cloud

One of our most important projects was the migration of all of our servers to the Béluga Cloud, Alliance/Calcul Québec's cloud infrastructure. This infrastructure will provide us with increased stability and performance, as well as greater service availability (24/7). This new infrastructure will also offer more autonomy and flexibility when it comes to our technical resource management.

+ Strengthening Interoperability

The interoperability of Érudit's services has been a priority for several years, with support from the Partenariat des Bibliothèques universitaires du Québec. Three main projects were realized to reach this objective:

1. Generation of a JATS Format

We implemented the conversion of the XML EruditArticle format to the XML JATS 1.3 Archiving format, compatible with the current production processes for our articles.

2. Automatic Generation of a PDF File

We implemented the conversion of the XML EruditArticle format to the PDF format, compatible with the current production processes for our articles. Journals with complete digital production processes for their articles can now request that a PDF be generated automatically.

3. Expansion of the OJS Gateway

The integration of Érudit's production processes with the Open Journal Systems (OJS) software was enhanced: we can now collect the final documents ready for publication directly from the OJS instances used by the journals. With these documents, on top of the metadata and the bibliographical information we were already collecting, we can create a complete XML file more quickly.

+ Maintenance and Optimization of Existing Services

Several projects were conducted to optimize Érudit's various services, notably for the maintenance of article production chains, the improvement of the production flow for books, and the creation of the KBART files. An important review of the accessibility of the portal's user interfaces on www.erudit.org was realized, along with an update to the Coalition Publica textual data corpus. Finally, we continued to improve cybersecurity for our technological infrastructure.

+ Migration of the Institutional Subscription Service

Since the external organization with which we were collaborating to manage institutional subscriptions have stopped operations, we had to quickly put an equivalent internal service in place.

+ Several New Projects

We started several important projects, notably the implementation of the ORCID and ROR identifiers, as well as the replacement of the tool used to track viewing statistics for journals. These projects will be ongoing in 2023–2024.

“Partnering with Érudit was one of the best strategic decisions that we made for the journals published by Iter Press.

We deeply appreciate their leadership and sage advice in the pragmatics of journal publication and grant applications, especially as we work toward full open access.

Congratulations on your 25th anniversary! We look forward to many more years of working together.”

Bill Bowen and Marian Cosic
Iter Press

Governance and Funding

Strategic Initiative of the Université de Montréal

Érudit was recognized as one of the Université de Montréal's seven **Strategic Initiatives in Research**. This important recognition underscores the increased support provided by the Vice-Rectorate of Research, Discovery, Creation and Innovation, and fits into the **Action Plan Research, Discovery, Creation and Innovation 2022-2027**.

Strategic Planning

As part of a collaboration with the PKP, notably around Coalition Publica, we have started brainstorming on the next strategic planning elements that each organization will be developing in the coming years. Supported by a team of facilitators, a steering committee made up of members of the Érudit, PKP and Coalition Publica teams designed each organization's strategic planning process to ensure that they were aligned with each other. The members of these teams, but also people from our extended community, were consulted in various ways during this important process.

Signature of the Dimensions Charter

The Érudit Consortium reinforced its commitment to promoting equity, diversity and inclusion with the signing of the Dimensions charter, a “pilot program to foster increased research excellence, innovation and creativity within the post-secondary sector across all disciplines, through greater equity, diversity and inclusion”. The Dimensions program charter addresses obstacles faced by underrepresented or disadvantaged groups, and recognizes the intersectionality that exists between the various facets of diversity. The Charter presents 8 principles that the signatory institutions commit to respect and apply, with the objective of achieving greater equity, diversity and inclusion.

[Read the charter](#)

Accessibility Statement

The Érudit Consortium is committed to making its erudit.org platform accessible to all, including people with disabilities, and has decided to publish its statement on this issue.

During the winter of 2023, as part of its commitment to **diversity, equity and inclusion (DEI)**, the team at Érudit established a working group tasked with evaluating the current accessibility level of the erudit.org platform and proposing improvements. This evaluation led to the statement of accessibility, which describes the contents and features which are accessible. In a perspective of continuous improvement, we will be working to solve the most important issues on that list as well as those identified by our community, including users, researchers, librarians and journal editorial teams. The statement of accessibility will evolve as progress is made on improvement implementation.

[Read the statement](#)

Composition of the Board

The Érudit team is supported in the management and development of the organization by its Board of Directors, made up of people involved in the fields of teaching and research, university libraries and scholarly publishing. The contribution of the members of our Board is essential to the vitality of Érudit and to its capacity to fulfill its mission. It is with gratitude that we acknowledge the exceptional contributions of our four outgoing members:

→ **Bernard Bizimana**

Observer representing the members of the CRKN,
Library Director, HEC Montréal

→ **Richard Marcoux**

Member representing the journals,
Scientific Committee for Érudit, full professor,
Sociology Department of the Université Laval

→ **Laurence Monnais**

Member representing the Université de Montréal,
former full professor, History Department, Scientific
Director of Presses de l'Université de Montréal

→ **Wendy Therrien**

Member representing Universities Canada,
External Relations and Research,
Universities Canada

A Warm Welcome to the New Members and Observers!

- **Mar González Palacios**
Associated Dean,
Collections and Content Strategy,
Simon Fraser University
- **Pascale Fournier**
Full professor and Research Chair in
Legal Pluralism and Comparative Law,
University of Ottawa
- **Francis Gingras**
Professor, Department of French Literature,
Université de Montréal and Scientific Director
of the Presses de l'Université de Montréal
- **Louis Houle**
Collection Services Director,
McGill University Library (observer
representing the members of the CRKN)

Team

Strengthening the Team

The last few years were particularly fruitful for Érudit and 2022–2023 was no exception. Whether through the journals newly added to the platform, the partnerships around open access or the new services offered, Érudit has been growing and, to support this growth, so has its team. New members were added to the team, bringing their expertise in communications, financial management and production, without forgetting research. We would also like to recognize the great expertise of long-standing Érudit employees who have been entrusted with greater responsibilities. Congratulations and thanks to the whole team!

**Congratulations
and thanks to
the whole team!**

Welcome to our new team members:

- **Félix-Antoine Allard**
Digital information technician
- **Suzanne Beth**
Research principal coordinator
- **Julie Brunelle**
Finance Officer
- **Catherine Côté-Cyr**
Communications Officer
- **Maxime Guénette**
Technical assistant
- **Audrey Larivière**
Data analyst
- **Anna Papakostidis**
Knowledge mobilization assistant

Welcome!

And congratulations to employees who saw their responsibilities evolve:

→ **Émilie Chouinard**
Product manager

→ **Jessica Clark**
Senior coordinator,
open access development

→ **Karine Fréchette**
Digital information
analyst

→ **Gwendal Henry**
Communications
advisor

→ **Guillaume Pellegrini**
Partnerships
coordination officer

Félicitations !

Émilie Paquin's Departure

From 2007 to 2023, Émilie Paquin has contributed to developing and defining Érudit's vision and strategy. In particular, she coordinated the drafting of major applications for grants, the roll-out of the Partnership for Open Access and the implementation of a Research and Strategy component. We want to celebrate the exceptional contribution she made to Érudit and to thank her warmly for her devotion.

Thank you!

Financial Statement

Income	2023	2022
■ Publishing and marketing services, partnerships for the open access	2,662,256	2,426,147
■ Government grants	1,905,582	1,521,271
■ Contributions of the three Consortium members	457,229	458,370
■ Other income	48,713	7,255
Total income	5,073,780	4,413,043

Expenses Charges	2023	2022
■ Publishing and marketing services, partnerships	2,297,569	2,035,189
■ Payroll and technology support services	2,577,594	2,028,737
■ Professional fees and subcontracting	151,794	140,801
■ Administration	113,234	78,232
■ Grants	110,188	62,000
■ Advertising and communications	56,249	19,887
Total expenses	5,306,628	4,364,846
Net income (Net loss)	-232,848	48,197

Financial Results

■ 2023 ■ 2022

Partners

Associated universities

Funding Bodies

Conseil de recherches en sciences humaines du Canada

Social Sciences and Humanities Research Council of Canada

Partners

The Érudit Consortium wants to thank all of its **institutional, public, and private partners** that have supported it for close to 25 years and which contribute to its success. A large network of organizations also supports the activities undertaken by Coalition Publica, our partnership with the Public Knowledge Project. The complete list is available in the [Community webpage](#).

Érudit²⁵

COALITION
PUBLICA

Graphic design by **Tatiana Matsoulevitch**